

Analysis of Roughness Correlations on Ice Geometries via Embedded Large-Eddy Simulation

Riccardo Gaudio*^{*}

*Institut für Strömungsmechanik, Technische Universität Braunschweig, 38108 Braunschweig, Germany
Department of Aerospace Science and Technology, Politecnico di Milano, 20156, Milan, Italy*

Denis Sotomayor-Zakharov[†] and Mariachiara Gallia[‡]

Institut für Strömungsmechanik, Technische Universität Braunschweig, 38108 Braunschweig, Germany

This study uses embedded large eddy simulations of a developing turbulent boundary layer over a heated flat plate with realistic ice roughness to assess local effects on velocity (ΔU^+) and thermal ($\Delta \Theta^+$) log-layer shifts. Validated against experimental data, the numerical setup is used to analyze the mean turbulent flow properties and ultimately assess a selection of equivalent sand grain roughness k_s correlations against computed roughness shifts. Several established models are taken into account that estimate equivalent sand grain roughness distributions based on geometric properties of the non-uniform rough surfaces. The trend of ΔU^+ and $\Delta \Theta^+$ is observed by employing the different correlations. The analysis is complemented with a brief assessment of Stanton number-friction factor analogies resulting from the simulation outputs. Finally, a multivariate approach is employed to investigate possible cross-dependencies between roughness geometrical properties and shifts. The results indicate that some existing models capture the trends of velocity shifts accurately only in the fully-rough regime for $k_s^+ > 400$, while for $k_s^+ < 400$, they generally struggle to correctly capture the expected trends. Thermal shifts show inconsistent trends across the tested models. The same gap appears in St estimates via friction analogies, showing no clear dependence on geometry features.

Nomenclature

$C_{(*)}$	=	Law of the wall constants [-]
c_f	=	Friction coefficient [-]
C_p	=	Air specific heat at constant pressure [J/(Kg · K)]

*Ph.D. Student, Institut für Strömungsmechanik, TU Braunschweig and Department of Aerospace Science and Technology, Politecnico di Milano, riccardo.gaudio@tu-braunschweig.de, AIAA Student Member (Corresponding Author)

[†]Ph.D. Research assistant, Institut für Strömungsmechanik, TU Braunschweig, Germany

[‡]Senior scientist, Institut für Strömungsmechanik, TU Braunschweig, Germany, mariachiara.gallia@tu-braunschweig.de, AIAA Member Young Professional

This paper is an extended version of the work presented at the AIAA AVIATION Forum and ASCEND, 21-21 July 2025, Las Vegas (NV), AIAA Paper No. 2025-3514.

ES_x	=	Streamwise surface effective slope [-]
H	=	Computational domain height [m]
Ku	=	Roughness kurtosis [-]
k_s	=	Equivalent sand grain roughness [m]
k_z	=	Roughness peak-to-valley height [m]
L	=	Reference plate length [m]
Pr, Pr_t	=	Molecular and turbulent Prandtl number [-]
q_w	=	Convective heat flux at wall [W/m ²]
R_a	=	Roughness arithmetic mean height [m]
Re_L	=	Reynolds number based on plate length [-]
Re_θ	=	Reynolds number based on boundary layer momentum thickness [-]
RA, RA_0	=	Rough and smooth surface Reynolds analogy factor [-]
R_q	=	Roughness RMS height [m]
$S_{(*)}$	=	Surface areas [m ²]
$S_{corr(*)}$	=	Corrected surface area ratio [-]
Sk	=	Roughness skewness [-]
St	=	Stanton number [-]
St_k	=	Roughness Stanton number [-]
t_f, t_s	=	Simulation and sampling time for ELES [s]
T_w	=	Wall temperature [K]
T_b	=	Flow bulk temperature [K]
T_τ	=	Friction temperature [K]
U_∞	=	Reference inflow velocity [m/s]
u	=	Flow velocity [m/s]
u_τ	=	Friction velocity [m/s]
α_x	=	Streamwise surface slope [°]
Δl	=	Mesh edge resolution [m]
Δx	=	Streamwise averaging resolution [m]
Δz	=	Computational domain span, and spanwise averaging resolution [m]
ΔU^+	=	Velocity log-layer shift in wall-units [-]
$\Delta \Theta^+$	=	Relative temperature log-layer shift in wall-units [-]
θ	=	Wall-relative temperature [K]

κ	=	von Kármán constant [-]
λ	=	Air thermal conductivity [W/(m · K)]
Λ_s	=	Solidity parameter [-]
μ	=	Air dynamic viscosity [Pa · s]
ν	=	Air kinematic viscosity [m ² /s]
ξ_{\min}	=	Minimum roughness wavelength [m]
ρ	=	Air density [kg/m ³]
τ_w	=	Shear stress at wall [Pa]

I. Introduction

In-flight icing poses a significant threat to aviation, degrading aerodynamic performance and potentially leading to serious consequences. The development of reliable numerical tools for ice prediction is crucial, serving as a faster and more cost-effective means within the certification processes of aircraft and rotorcraft. Recent advancements in codes such as GlennICE [1], FENSAP-ICE [2], IGLOO2D/3D [3], PoliMice [4], or DICEPS [5] have improved accuracy of predictions, especially for rime ice, yet challenges remain especially for glaze conditions as highlighted in the Ice Prediction Workshops [6, 7]. A critical issue is the effect of ice roughness on surrounding airflow, which significantly impacts skin friction and heat transfer rates. It is known that such quantities govern the freezing rate when the droplets do not freeze on impact, thus requiring precise characterization of their enhancement due to roughness [8].

Icing codes often employ RANS or boundary layer methods to simulate flow around evolving ice shapes, incorporating surface roughness via an equivalent sand-grain roughness height k_s [9, 10]. Colebrook and White [11] firstly introduced k_s as an equivalent height for irregular, and non-uniform rough surfaces that produce the same mean effects on the flow as the uniform, hemispherical sand-grain of Nikuradse [12] experiments in the fully rough regime. Though this simplifies simulations, icing codes often rely on a reversed-engineered k_s , determined indirectly to match experimental ice shapes, resulting in a potential misrepresentation of the physical interactions driving the enhancement mechanisms. Moreover, the treatment of convective heat transfer effects is frequently linked to skin friction, even if the Reynolds analogy fails to hold in the presence of roughness. Some of the older implementations typically assume uniform k_s values based on general icing conditions, as seen in LEWICE [13], although not always aligned with experimental observations, which reveal significantly non-uniform roughness trends [14, 15]. Alternative approaches employ non-uniform surface roughness models [16] or enhancement factors that adjust smooth-surface convective heat transfer as done in GlennICE [1], although once again calibrated to match experimental ice shapes. A more effective strategy could involve correlating k_s directly with geometric and statistical surface parameters. The development of a universally applicable k_s model is of high importance, as several studies related to rough wall-bounded flows [17, 18] pointed out relations of this parameter

to the wall shear stress τ_w and heat flux q_w via a velocity shift ΔU^+ and thermal shift $\Delta\Theta^+$ in the mean turbulent profiles log-layer, respectively. These shifts are commonly described as functions of the equivalent sand grain roughness height in wall-units $k_s^+ = k_s u_\tau / \nu$, where ν is the kinematic viscosity of the fluid and $u_\tau = \sqrt{\tau_w / \rho}$ is the friction velocity, with ρ being the density of the fluid. The concept of roughness shifts stems from the fundamental observation that the log-law region of a boundary layer is displaced from its smooth formulation when exposed to a rough surface. As a consequence, the velocity and thermal log-law regions can be formulated as in Eq. (1) and Eq. (2), respectively, with $y^+ = y u_\tau / \nu$, $u^+ = u / u_\tau$ and $\theta^+ = (T_w - T) / T_\tau$. Here, T_w is the surface temperature, and $T_\tau = q_w / (\rho C_P u_\tau)$ is the friction temperature normally used to scale the relative difference of the flow temperature with respect to the wall, with C_P being the specific heat at constant pressure of the fluid.

$$u^+ = \frac{1}{\kappa} \ln(y^+) + C^+ - \Delta U^+ \quad (1)$$

$$\theta^+ = \frac{Pr_t}{\kappa} \ln(y^+) + C_\theta^+ - \Delta\Theta^+ \quad (2)$$

The von Kármán constant is commonly assumed as $\kappa \simeq 0.4$, while values for the smooth surface velocity and thermal constants are proposed in literature as $C^+ \simeq 5.0$ and $C_\theta^+ \simeq 13.2Pr - 5.3$ [19, 20]. The Prandtl number is defined as $Pr = C_P \mu / \lambda$, with $\mu = \rho \nu$ representing the dynamic viscosity and λ the thermal conductivity of the fluid. The turbulent Prandtl number Pr_t presents a wider definition and a more complex behavior, but is normally assumed as constant $Pr_t \simeq 0.85 - 0.9$ through the boundary layer for numerical simulations.

Experimental evidence shows that ΔU^+ is close to zero for small k_s^+ (hydraulically smooth regime) and tends to exhibit a monotonically growing behavior for large k_s^+ , commonly identifying the fully rough regime (see Eq. (3)). In such regime, local flow separation and pressure effects dominate over viscous effects. Intermediate values of k_s^+ define the transitionally rough regime, where viscous effects are still relevant and ΔU^+ is also affected by the surface topology. For k_s^+ falling in this regime, correlations can be found in literature as the one proposed by Grigson [21], shown in Eq. (4) and covering the entire roughness scale spectrum based on the data of Colebrook and White [11]. Finally, it must be pointed out that most RANS tools use modified boundary conditions to account for ΔU^+ in the boundary layer adjacent to a surface with a specific k_s , see for example Aupoix [22].

$$\Delta U^+ = \frac{1}{\kappa} \ln(k_s^+) + C^+ - 8.5 \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta U^+ = \frac{1}{\kappa} \ln \left(1 + \frac{k_s^+}{e^{[\kappa(C^+ - 8.5)]}} \right) \quad (4)$$

The asymptotic form of $\Delta\Theta^+$ in the fully rough regime remains ambiguous, with disagreement among current models [23]. For example, Owen and Thomson [24] developed the correlation reported in Eq. (5), including roughness

effects based on the parameter St_k defined in Eq. (6) with $C_k = 1.923$, $a = -0.45$ and $b = -0.8$ being topology-related constants. The correlation suggests an early increase of $\Delta\Theta^+$ approaching $k_s^+ \approx 100$, followed by a decrease of $\Delta\Theta^+$ as k_s^+ increases into fully rough. In alternative, more recent studies evidence a tendency of a constant $\Delta\Theta^+ \approx 4$ in the fully rough regime [18, 25].

$$\Delta\Theta^+ = \frac{Pr_t}{\kappa} \ln(k_s^+) + C_\theta^+ - \frac{1}{St_k} - 7.2 \quad (5)$$

$$St_k = C_k (k_s^+)^a Pr^b \quad (6)$$

With relation to roughness shifts, different correlations for engineering applications that link k_s to geometrical features have been developed, among others, by Sigal and Danberg [26], Bons [27], Flack and Schultz [28], and Forooghi et al. [17]. These correlations are typically based on experimental or numerical data from various roughness samples, considering multiple statistical and geometrical parameters, with k_s effects on mean flow introduced via the aforementioned log-layer shifts. Notably, most studies focus on skin friction enhancements, with fewer addressing thermal shifts, limiting robust k_s model development for heat transfer.

The convective heat transfer has been extensively linked to friction on smooth and rough surfaces. Early studies [29, 30] focused on providing a relation for the Stanton number St in pipes as a function of the skin friction coefficient c_f , the Reynolds number and the molecular Prandtl number, combining analytical considerations with experimental data. While this analogy was found to provide satisfactory results on smooth surfaces with comparable molecular and turbulent Prandtl numbers, later investigations showed how the proportionality between St and c_f is compromised in the presence of surface roughness. This was observed on wind turbine roughness by Bons [31], who noted that the increase of the Stanton number is generally accompanied by a larger increase of the skin friction coefficient. The phenomenon is explained by the rise in pressure drag induced by roughness and contributing to friction, which finds no analog in heat transfer enhancement mechanisms. Empirical $St - c_f$ analogies have been proposed based on Re and Pr by Martinelli [29], or based on the Reynolds analogy factor $RA = 2St/c_f$ by Forooghi et al. [32]. Through a DNS study on random roughness, Peeters and Sandham [33] assessed these and additional analogies demonstrating how their performance depends on the roughness regime, delivering St predictions that might increasingly deviate from the simulated one as the roughness parameter k^+ is varied.

Comprehensive experimental and numerical databases on artificial or realistic roughness are the base to build k_s correlations and $St - c_f$ analogies. However, applications within the icing field are still limited. A series of studies at Baylor University focused on heat transfer and skin friction measurement over laser-scanned ice surfaces [34–36]. Alternatively, high-fidelity numerical techniques such as Large Eddy Simulation (LES) or Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS) can be used to evaluate enhancement mechanisms, with the advantage of undisturbed access to turbulent boundary layer properties down to roughness level. Hybrid RANS-LES methods are reported in literature,

but they were mainly used to target flow separation and aerodynamic performance degradation due to ice accretion, modeling small geometric features [37, 38]. Resolving roughness requires LES or DNS of realistic surfaces down to the near-wall region, typically conducted in canonical wall-bounded flow configurations to manage computational costs. These simulations often involve artificial or realistic roughness in periodic channels or flat plate setups. Several studies have performed DNS and LES in periodic channels with wall roughness [32, 39, 40], including Yang et al. [41], who applied these configurations to realistic ice from engine nacelles. While periodic channels effectively simulate fully developed turbulent boundary layers with uniform roughness, they are far from realistic applications. Indeed, such configuration excludes any roughness inhomogeneity due to the periodicity constrain, thus neglecting any turbulent flow history influence, and imposes a constant boundary layer to roughness height ratio. In contrast, flat plate setups eventually including pressure gradient effects allow the analysis of developing boundary layers under more realistic conditions, albeit at a higher computational cost. Extensive effort was dedicated to study developing boundary layers on rough surfaces without considering thermal effects. Several of these studies are reviewed in Piomelli [42], which also includes an overview of different types of rough surfaces analysed. Pressure gradient configurations, which might be considered closer to operating airfoil conditions, were tested in Yuan and Piomelli [43] and Yuan and Piomelli [44] over sand-paper roughness. Here, roughness presence was found to obstacle the flow quasi-laminarization normally induced by flow acceleration on turbulent boundary layers over smooth walls. Another crucial aspect commonly analysed with a flat plate setup is boundary layer transition. As an example, the recent study by Ananth et al. [45] used a LES approach to study transition to turbulence over a realistic roughness strip. Contrarily to momentum, thermal effects where less investigated for turbulent boundary layers. Insights into rough ZPG heated flat plates DNS can be found in Cardillo et al. [46], employing recycling and rescaling methods to establish turbulent inlet conditions. Zabaleta et al. [47] performed Wall-Modeled LES of a turbulent boundary layer over a heated plate featuring realistic ice roughness from previous experiments McCarrell et al. [36], providing a comparison of the numerical setup with measurements of convective heat transfer by taking into account solid conduction. In a similar way, Sotomayor-Zakharov et al. [48] verified and validated an embedded, Wall-Resolved LES setup against the same reference study. Both this work confirmed good accuracy achieved by LES strategies in capturing thermal convection when compared to experimental data.

The present work assesses the performance of equivalent sand grain roughness models thought for engineering application on a realistic ice geometry based on an Embedded, Wall-Resolved LES (ELES) approach. In this type of simulation, the LES domain is restricted around the region of interest, being in this case the rough boundary layer. Elsewhere, flow is simulated through a RANS approach, reducing significantly the computational burden. The objective of the proposed investigation is to link k_s with the observed flow properties, for which the effect of realistic ice roughness is systematically evaluated through velocity and temperature shifts correlation extracted from ELES simulations of ZPG turbulent boundary layers. The employed numerical setup is the one verified and validated in the work from Sotomayor-Zakharov et al. [48]. Two realistic, unwrapped ice geometries taken from McCarrell et al. [36] are included

into a flat plate flow configuration, and inlet condition are varied to access wider roughness regimes in terms of k_s^+ . Mean turbulent profiles shifts with respect to theoretical smooth log-layers are computed, and the resulting data points, covering the transitionally ($5 < k_s^+ < 70$) and fully rough ($k_s^+ > 70$) regimes [19] are used to compare the performance of k_s models in predicting roughness effects on the mean flow. Roughness shifts are evaluated against few correlations from literature that make use of statistical moments, surface slope-related parameters, or solidity, combined to build a relation for k_s/k_{ref} , being k_{ref} a reference roughness measure. A similar k_s model assessment can be found in McClain and Boldt [49], where the authors analyzed the geometrical behavior of the models applied to several ice geometries. However, in such study flow properties are not taken into account, thus disregarding any correlation of k_s with roughness shifts. Finally, few $St - c_f$ analogies from literature are assessed for the present numerical results, and a multivariate approach is proposed to observe cross-dependencies between computed shifts and rough surface properties. The paper is structured as follows: Section II presents the analysis methods, including the simulated ice geometries characterization, the numerical set-up and test cases, and the strategy to extract turbulent quantities and roughness shifts from the outputs; Section III presents the main results in terms of model-based k_s^+ correlations with ΔU^+ and $\Delta \theta^+$, $St - c_f$ analogies, and multivariate analysis of surface geometrical features; Section IV finally draws conclusions and future perspectives of the work.

II. Methodology

The Embedded Large Eddy Simulations (ELES) carried out in this study aim to replicate the experimental conditions established by McCarrell et al. [36]. While the geometries have been slightly adapted for the numerical domain, the essential statistical properties remain consistent with the original experiments. The following sections will provide a concise overview of the experimental setup, followed by the description of the computational domain, mesh, and numerical method. Subsequently, a detailed characterization of the ice surfaces is proposed before providing an introduction of the equivalent sand grain roughness correlations under analysis. Finally, a description of the numerical test cases employed in this work and details on post-processing techniques are given.

A. Experimental database

The evaluation of equivalent sand grain models against LES results on realistic ice roughness is conducted based on the ice roughness geometries described in McCarrell et al. [36], who unwrapped the original wind tunnel NACA0012 ice scans by McClain et al. [50] using the Self-Organizing-Maps approach of McClain and Kreeger [51]. By scaling up 10 times the geometries, considering just the suction side ice pattern and adding a smooth portion in front of the roughness, flat plate test articles for the measurement of skin friction and heat transfer were deployed. The NACA0012 Reynolds number was matched by correspondingly reducing the test velocity by a factor 10. The test articles were 3D printed into 2 materials, namely aluminum and plastic, to determine the effects of heat conduction within the solid layer

on the convective heat transfer resulting from measurements. The rough plate substrate was divided into panels, each one instrumented to control the surface heating and possibly provide a uniform heat-flux across the whole surface. The convective heat transfer and the skin friction were evaluated at every panel by means of infrared thermography and hot-film anemometry, respectively, resulting in Stanton number St and friction coefficient c_f distributions along the plate. Further details can be found in the original paper, while Table 1 resumes the reference flow conditions matching the experiments of McCarrell et al. [36]. Here, L is the test article reference length, T_b the air bulk temperature at which fluid properties are considered, $\Delta T = (T_w - T_\infty)$ the relative temperature difference between wall and freestream, ρ the air density, C_P the specific heat at constant pressure, μ the air dynamic viscosity, λ its thermal conductivity, and Re_L and Pr the Reynolds number based on the plate length and Prandtl number resulting from such conditions.

Table 1 Conditions and flow properties for numerical simulations

L	U_∞	T_b	ΔT	ρ	C_P	μ	λ	$Re_L \cdot 10^{-5}$	Pr
[m]	[ms^{-1}]	[K]	[K]	[kg/m^3]	[J/kg·K]	[Pa·s]	[W/m·K]	[-]	[-]
0.9525	6.67	300	10	1.124	1007	$1.858 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.565 \cdot 10^{-2}$	3.85	0.729

Fig. 1 Elevation map of rough test articles 113012.05 (left) and 113012.04 (right) [36].

B. Characterization of rough surfaces

The two ice geometries displayed in Fig. 1 are used as baseline for the present study, corresponding to the labels 113012.05 and 113012.04 from McCarrell et al. [36], here conveniently referred to as case 1 and case 2, respectively. Such geometries are adapted to a numerical domain for an ELES of a ZPG flat plate. The main modifications regard the spanwise (z) extension of the rough surfaces, which were reduced from $\Delta z_0 = 0.2032$ m to $\Delta z = 0.05$ m to spare computational cost, and a filtering of the spanwise edge section of the domain to blend the roughness levels onto a unique height values, thus ensuring periodicity across z required from simulations. From a physical standpoint, this

could lead to roughness features loss and turbulence constriction. However, as shown in detail in Sotomayor-Zakharov et al. [48], such surface manipulation does not affect critically results in the turbulent boundary layer over the rough plate.

To link the computed shifts to simulated geometrical properties, the analysis for the present work is directly based on the processed surfaces used for the simulations, which already underwent the modifications listed above. The surface characterization targets statistical and geometrical indicators entering the k_s models considered in this work, that will be described in the next section. The flat plate wall featuring roughness elevation $k = k(x, z)$ is divided in several sections in streamwise (x) direction, each of fixed extension Δx and planform area S , covering the full plate length L . For each section, statistical moments such as mean height k_m , arithmetic average R_a , RMS height R_q , skewness Sk , and kurtosis Ku are computed according to their definition (see Eqs. (7a)-(7e)) to deliver a distribution along x .

$$k_m = \frac{1}{S} \int_S k \, dS \quad (7a)$$

$$R_a = \frac{1}{S} \int_S |k - k_m| \, dS \quad (7b)$$

$$R_q = \sqrt{\frac{1}{S} \int_S (k - k_m)^2 \, dS} \quad (7c)$$

$$Sk = \frac{1}{S R_q^3} \int_S (k - k_m)^3 \, dS \quad (7d)$$

$$Ku = \frac{1}{S R_q^4} \int_S (k - k_m)^4 \, dS \quad (7e)$$

In addition, parameters as the effective slope ES_x and the local surface slope α_x in streamwise direction can be retrieved according to Eqs. (8) and (9), where $\partial k / \partial x$ represents the surface height gradient along x . From the slope distribution, the weighted root-mean-square (RMS) approach proposed by McClain and Boldt [49] is here employed to retrieve the corresponding RMS variation across the height map ($\alpha_{x,\text{RMS}}$), as shown in Eq. (10). It can be seen that the wet area S_w (defined in Eq. (11)) is used to compute this value, and that only windward elements are considered, identified as those featuring a negative x-component of the local normal vector $\vec{n} = (n_x, n_z, n_k)$.

$$ES_x = \frac{1}{S} \int_S \left| \frac{\partial k}{\partial x} \right| \, dS \quad (8)$$

$$\alpha_x = \arctan \left(\frac{\partial k}{\partial x} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$\alpha_{x,\text{RMS}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{S_w} \int_{S_w} \alpha_x^2 \cdot H(n_x < 0) \, dS_w} \quad (10)$$

$$S_w = \int_S \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\partial k}{\partial x}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial k}{\partial z}\right)^2} dS \quad (11)$$

C. Equivalent sand grain roughness correlations

In the following, the equivalent sand grain roughness models considered for the assessment are briefly introduced. By collecting data from several artificial and realistic roughness samples, Flack and Schultz [28] proposed a correlation solely based on surface statistical moments, namely RMS height R_q and skewness Sk , as presented in Eq. (12).

$$\frac{k_s}{R_q} = 4.43(1 + Sk)^{1.37} \quad (12)$$

A different approach was pursued by Forooghi et al. [17], who investigated the effects of several surface parameters on k_s by means of direct numerical simulation (DNS) of channel flows at $Re_\tau \simeq 500$ with different wall geometries, featuring random synthetic roughness. In such study, the authors pointed out that skewness and effective slope (ES_x) were found to satisfactorily predict k_s normalized with maximum peak-to-valley roughness height k_z . The corresponding correlation is presented in Eq. (13). In the original study, an additional parameter Δ was included representing the distribution of roughness element sizes as a measure of diversity of roughness peak heights. However, Eq. (13) is modified only for values of Δ close to zero, which according to the authors correspond to roughness with near-uniform peak size, thus not likely to be found in naturally formed ice roughness [49]. Therefore, this parameter is excluded from the present analysis for the ice roughness case, and Eq. (13) is always considered.

$$\frac{k_s}{k_z} = (0.67Sk^2 + 0.93Sk + 1.3)[1.07(1 - e^{-3.5ES_x})] \quad (13)$$

It is worth to stress the fact that the above correlations were built specifically to cover the fully rough behavior, thus obtained exploiting Eq. (3), and that may suffer in the representation of lower levels of roughness in the transitionally rough regime. A different series of correlation is based on geometrical feature such as solidity and slope, and most relevant examples are provided by Sigal and Danberg [26] and Bons [27]. The first study introduced the parameter Λ_s , representing a solidity factor containing both surface slope and shape information. Λ_s is defined in Eq. (14), where S , S_f , and S_s are the surface planform area, the total frontal area of the roughness, and the total windward wet surface, respectively. Based on its definition, Λ_s can be obtained along the flat plate under analysis following the approach presented previously, and computing for each streamwise section S , S_f , and S_s based on local roughness characteristics. Sigal and Danberg [26] determined a k_s correlation from roughness geometry for surfaces with uniformly-sized and uniformly-shaped two-dimensional (bars, ribs, or circular rods) roughness elements arranged in a uniform pattern along

a test surface, delivering the function found in Eq. (15). The resulting model was determined based on the values of the log-law intercept in presence of roughness. The definition of a k_{ref} to scale k_s is ambiguous in the reference work. In this study, k_z is used as for the Forooghi et al. [17] correlation.

$$\Lambda_s = \left(\frac{S}{S_f} \right) \left(\frac{S_f}{S_s} \right)^{-1.6} \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{k_s}{k_z} = \begin{cases} 0.00321 \Lambda_s^{4.925} & 1.4 \leq \Lambda_s < 4.89 \\ 8.0 & 4.89 \leq \Lambda_s \leq 13.25 \\ 151.71 \Lambda_s^{-1.138} & \Lambda_s > 13.25 \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

Bons [27] resorted instead to a purely slope-based correlation, relating k_s/R_a to the root-mean-square variation of the local rough surface slope, as seen in Eq. (16). Bons [27] measured skin friction (c_f) and heat transfer (St) for low-speed flow over turbine surfaces from 3D scanned data. Slope values α were measured from 2D streamwise traces of such roughness patches, and this can be considered equivalent to computing them in the x-direction as indicated by Eq. (9). The RMS value was then evaluated over the entire surface. Established c_f correlations were used to fit experimental data to extract k_s estimates. While c_f values aligned with previous sandgrain roughness models, St correlations based on Reynolds analogies were found to overpredict heat transfer. In the attempt to overcome previous models limitations in the transitionally rough regime, Bons [27] presented a tuned correlation for $k_s^+ < 70$. Moreover, the analysis indicated that real roughness differs significantly from regularly shaped models, affecting in particular the accuracy of St predictions. These findings expose limitations in traditional roughness models and the use of ordered roughness elements.

$$\frac{k_s}{R_a} = 0.0736 \alpha_{x,\text{RMS}} + 0.019 \alpha_{x,\text{RMS}}^2 \quad (16)$$

D. $St - c_f$ analogies

Convective heat transfer is frequently estimated by friction analogies. The limitations of such approach on rough surfaces have been evidenced by previous works [31], still adjusted correlations have been proposed to provide St estimates. These relations have an empirical base, stemming from simulation or experimental data, which directly link St to c_f based on the rationale of the Reynolds analogy. While the latter is known to fail in presence of wall roughness, corrected models have been devised, including dependence on flow conditions through the Prandtl and Reynolds number. Among others, Martinelli [29] proposed the relation of Eq. (17). Based on the cavity vortex hypotheses applied to experimental data on 3D irregular roughness, Owen and Thomson [24] derived constants for the roughness Stanton number St_k , as previously indicated in Eq. (6), which acts as a thermal resistance to include cavity stagnation effects. The resulting form of St_k can be used to derived a rough Reynolds analogy factor $RA = (2St/c_f)$ as indicated in

Eq. (18). More recently, researchers have sought after a generally applicable relation between the Reynolds analogy factor and the wall roughness parameter k_s , as done for example by Forooghi et al. [32], resulting in the model of Eq. (19). Here, the subscript 0 refers to smooth conditions. Such correlation was obtained from a DNS study of periodic channels focusing on density and slope parameters, thus generating roughness elements by systematically modifying their distribution based on a truncated conical section. To complement such analysis, realistic roughness scans from wind turbine blades and combustion chamber deposits were considered. By knowing the theoretical distribution of c_f and St on a smooth plate, the corresponding rough values can be estimated based on local friction and k_s^+ .

$$\left(\frac{2St}{c_f}\right) = 5\sqrt{c_f/2} \left[Pr + \ln(1 + 5Pr) + \frac{1}{2} \ln\left((Re/60)\sqrt{c_f/2}\right) \right] \quad (17)$$

$$RA = \frac{1}{Pr_t + \sqrt{c_f/2} St_k^{-1}} \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{RA}{RA_0} = 0.55 + 0.45 \exp[-k_s^+/130] \quad (19)$$

As part of the present study, these different analogies will be assessed to further investigate their applicability on a turbulent boundary layer, similarly to what Peeters and Sandham [33] did for a turbulent periodic channel setup. Notably, the type of roughness used in this study is different, for example, from the one investigated in Forooghi et al. [32], thus testing once again its applicability in a substantially different context.

E. Numerical setup and model

The numerical simulations follow the same procedures applied in the study of Sotomayor-Zakharov et al. [48], which used the software ANSYS FLUENT 21R2 to perform ELES on an airfoil with ice accreted around the leading edge. Said study also includes the verification and validation of the LES setup for standard flow configurations against wind tunnel measurements. Figure 2 depicts the flow domain, which follows the experimental configuration of McCarrell et al. [36] but is extended in the streamwise direction for numerical purposes. The ZPG heated flat plate extends from $x = 0$ m to $x = 4.064$ m, although the experimental test surface only extends to $x = 0.9525$ m, taken as the reference scale L . The height of the numerical domain $H = 0.3048$ m corresponds to the wind tunnel test section height. A computational box with a reduced span was selected, as outlined before, extending from $z_{\min} = -\Delta z/2$ to $z_{\max} = \Delta z/2$, which manages to approximately preserve the surface statistical parameters of the full span domain, and the proper development of turbulent structures as demonstrated in [48]. Specifically, it was proven in such study that the selected $\Delta z = 0.05$ m was sufficient to resolve the roughness features and capture the turbulent structures developing by performing a sensitivity analysis on such parameter. A double domain span $\Delta z = 0.10$ m was found to deliver similar R_q and Sk distributions,

and comparable turbulent mean profiles and stresses.

The domain is divided into three subdomains (see Fig. 2): a laminar subdomain, a LES subdomain in the center, and a RANS subdomain downstream. The upstream subdomain allows the laminar boundary layer to develop over the smooth portion of the flat plate before roughness is encountered. Inside the LES subdomain, transition to turbulence is triggered by the rough surface. The turbulent boundary layer keeps developing into the downstream RANS subdomain crossing a LES-RANS interface. A non-turbulent flow with velocity $U_\infty = 6.67 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ and temperature $T_\infty = 295 \text{ K}$ enters the domain at the inlet, initially without any turbulent content, eventually developed due to roughness presence. The flat plate acts as a no-slip wall and is maintained at a constant wall temperature $T_w = 305 \text{ K} > T_\infty$ to generate a heat flux. The isothermal boundary condition was proved to adequately capture heat transfer in the turbulent region, which is the target of the analysis, as detailed in the related validation study [48]. The first bottom portion of the laminar subdomain is set as a symmetry (slip-region) to ensure a laminar inflow reaching the plate, whose smooth portion begins at $x/L = 0$. The sides of the laminar subdomain are set as symmetries as well, preventing boundary layer formation there, while the sides of the LES and RANS subdomains are periodic interfaces. The top faces of each domain present a symmetry boundary condition, complying with the reference wind tunnel experimental setup.

Fig. 2 Flow domain scheme in non-dimensional units (x/L). The blue coloring indicates the heated plate crossing the three subdomains.

The rough surface is discretized by means of a body-fitted, adaptive Cartesian mesh within the LES subdomain, featuring cubic elements of side Δl that are progressively refined close to the plate. The maximum edge size of a cubic element is $\Delta l_{\max} = 0.0064 \text{ m}$, while the minimum resolution close to the wall is set to $\Delta l_{\min} = 4 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}$. This results in five mesh resolution levels that progressively halve their edge size from Δl_{\max} to Δl_{\min} . Near the flat plate, the Cartesian mesh merges with a prismatic layer with a first layer height of $2 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m}$, a growth ratio of 1.15, and a number of layers chosen to achieve a last layer height of $1/2 \cdot \Delta l_{\min}$. A close-up view of the near-wall mesh structure for the case 1 geometry is given in Fig. 3. These settings ensure a first cell height $\Delta y_w^+ < 1$ for simulations, with an average $\Delta y^+ \approx 0.2$ for the highest Re_L cases. Moreover, $4 \lesssim \Delta l^+ \lesssim 30$ for the two geometries is achieved, aligned with previous

Fig. 3 Near wall mesh structure for case 1.

LES on rough surfaces [39, 44]. A minimum roughness wavelength ξ_{\min} based on the 99% threshold PSD spectrum energy of the surfaces in the critical roughness region between $x/L = 0.3$ and $x/L = 0.8$ was extracted to evaluate the employed surface resolution. For case 1, $\xi_{\min} \sim 8.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m, while case 2 resulted in $\xi_{\min} \sim 9.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m. From this, it was concluded that $\Delta l_{\min} \lesssim \xi_{\min}/12$ was sufficient to correctly resolve the surface topology, according to previous DNS studies on roughness [52]. For the laminar and RANS subdomains, a hexahedral mesh is generated, matching the prisms layer growth from the wall and expanding outwards from the interfaces with the LES region. A grid sensitivity study is included in Sotomayor-Zakharov et al. [48], where the minimum and maximum resolution were progressively halved to show the effects on key parameters and turbulence statistics.

The ELES solves an incompressible, ZPG boundary layer modeled by the momentum and scalar transport equations (20) and (21) for the velocity components u_i and the scalar $\theta = T_w - T$ representing the wall-relative temperature of the flow.

$$\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u_i u_j}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\mu}{\rho} \frac{\partial^2 u_i}{\partial x_j^2} \quad (20)$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u_j \theta}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\lambda}{\rho C_P} \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial x_j^2} \quad (21)$$

Within the Laminar subdomain, these equations are solved directly, excluding any turbulence modeling, to provide a laminar inflow by deactivating turbulence production. The WALE model [53] with $C_w = 0.325$ is used for the LES, while the SST $k-\omega$ model [54] is applied in the downstream RANS subdomain, thus modifying Eqs. (20) and (21) into RANS form. The energy equation is enabled without viscous heating due to low flow speeds, using $Pr_{\text{sgs}} = 0.85$ for LES and $Pr_t = 0.85$ for RANS. A non-iterative time advancement (NITA) solver with a second-order implicit scheme is used, along with a PISO scheme for pressure-velocity coupling. The least-squares cell-based gradient method is implemented, with a bounded central difference scheme (BCD) for the LES and a second-order upwind scheme for laminar and RANS

region. ELES simulations are initialized from a preliminary RANS solution with a perturbation to trigger turbulence. The initializing RANS simulation uses the SST $k-\omega \gamma - Re_\theta$ model [55] to establish a developing laminar boundary layer before the rough zone. The simulation is run with a time step Δt small enough to ensure, for each case, an average CFL < 0.5 . The computed convective flow-time $t'_f = U_\infty t_f / L \sim 2$ was long-enough to observe a statistically converged behavior of flow monitors such as c_f and St , enabling statistic collection for an additional flow-time $t'_s = U_\infty t_s / L \sim 2.5$. This choice is based on the statistical convergence analysis included in Sotomayor-Zakharov et al. [48], where more insights into the choice of the numerical settings are also reported.

F. Surface quantities and roughness shifts evaluation

From numerical results, wall quantities such as τ_w and q_w require evaluation along the plate to derive c_f and St distributions and local friction quantities for wall-units scaling (u_τ, T_τ). The approach followed by Sotomayor-Zakharov et al. [48] is used. As done for surface statistics, the plate is divided in several streamwise segments (n -indexing), corresponding to a limited mesh set of N points on a projected area $S = \Delta x \times \Delta z$. Using time-averaged surface values of pressure p_n , shear stress $\vec{\tau}_n$ and heat flux q_n from simulations, τ_w and q_w are locally averaged over these subsets for each streamwise x -location as shown in Eqs. (22) and (23), respectively. Here, $\vec{\eta}_n$ represents the local surface element normal, while \vec{e}_x is the x direction unit vector. From these, c_f and St can be obtained via Eqs. (24) and (25).

$$\tau_w = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{n=1}^N S_n [(\vec{\tau}_n \cdot \vec{e}_x) - p_n (\vec{\eta}_n \cdot \vec{e}_x)] \quad (22)$$

$$q_w = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{n=1}^N S_n q_n \quad (23)$$

$$c_f = \frac{2 \tau_w}{\rho U_\infty^2} \quad (24)$$

$$St = \frac{q_w}{\rho C_P U_\infty \Delta T} \quad (25)$$

Mean turbulent quantities are obtained through a double-averaging procedure. Each time averaged field of interest $\overline{\varphi}$ is further averaged in x and z over each segment along the rough plate through the operator $\langle \cdot \rangle$ defined in Equation (26), thus resulting in a plane-average procedure as used for example in Piomelli and Yuan [56].

$$\langle \varphi(x_n, y) \rangle = \frac{1}{S} \int_{x_n - \frac{\Delta x}{2}}^{x_n + \frac{\Delta x}{2}} \int_{-\frac{\Delta z}{2}}^{\frac{\Delta z}{2}} \overline{\varphi}(x, y, z) dx dz \quad (26)$$

The spatial resolutions Δx and Δz , employed to compute the averaged surface properties and turbulent profiles, were chosen consistently with the reference experimental [36] and numerical [48] setups, respectively. Note that Δz coincides with the computational domain span. Double-averaged turbulent profiles $\langle u \rangle^+$ and $\langle \theta \rangle^+$ are scaled in wall

units, indicated by the superscript (+), by means of friction velocity u_τ and temperature T_τ . These scaling properties are locally computed using τ_w and q_w as shown in eq. (27) and eq. (28).

$$u_\tau = \sqrt{\frac{\tau_w}{\rho}} \quad (27)$$

$$T_\tau = \frac{q_w}{\rho C_P u_\tau} \quad (28)$$

The wall-distance y^+ is scaled via eq. (29). The turbulent profiles extraction accounts for the local origin of the wall, which amounts to displace the wall-normal distance y by the mean roughness elevation k_m (as defined in Eq. (7a)), which acts as the virtual origin of the rough wall. Both y and k_m are measured with respect to the same reference plane, corresponding to the smooth plate level.

$$y^+ = \frac{\rho u_\tau (y - k_m)}{\mu} \quad (29)$$

The effects of roughness on the flow field are analyzed through the examination of profiles $\langle u \rangle^+$ and $\langle \theta \rangle^+$ extracted at various locations x along the plate to facilitate the assessment of boundary layer evolution. These locations coincide with the plate segments centers x_n , but only the ones in the fully developed boundary layer region. Among the test cases, the evaluation locations x are held constant to analyze turbulent flow properties at consistent roughness levels. To evaluate the k_s models from the literature, roughness shifts ΔU^+ and $\Delta \Theta^+$ must be extracted from these mean turbulent profiles. Yuan and Piomelli [44] suggested a method for this evaluation concerning rough flat plate simulations under a favorable pressure gradient (FPG) condition, which utilizes the diagnostic functions $K_u^+ = y^+(du^+/dy^+)$ and $K_\theta^+ = y^+(d\Theta^+/dy^+)$. These diagnostic indicators allow for the identification of log layers in the velocity and thermal profiles, characterized by the plateau regions displayed in the functions. Based on this argument, log-layers are individuated for each profile by examining the behavior of dK_u^+/dy^+ and dK_θ^+/dy^+ as further outlined in Sec. III.B. Values of ΔU^+ and $\Delta \Theta^+$ refers to local profile shifts from theoretical smooth log-law profiles, i.e. $u_s^+ = 1/\kappa \ln(y^+) + C^+$ and $\Theta_s^+ = Pr_t/\kappa \ln(y^+) + C_\theta^+$ (see Eqs. (1) and (2)). The shifts can be directly obtained as indicated in Eq. (30). For cases with varied velocity, the log-layer location is verified to be reasonably not affected by the change in inlet conditions in the fully turbulent region.

$$\Delta U^+ = u_s^+(y_{rs}^+) - u^+(y_{rs}^+) \quad \Delta \Theta^+ = \Theta_s^+(y_{rs}^+) - \Theta^+(y_{rs}^+) \quad (30)$$

G. Test cases

The test cases under analysis are simulated under the reference flow conditions matching the experiments (see Table 1). Additional simulations are conducted by progressively reducing the reference inlet velocity U_∞ for both geometries. The main purpose is to cover a wider range of k_s^+ through a variation of the plate Reynolds number Re_L

presented in Eq. (31).

$$Re_L = \frac{U_\infty L}{\nu} \quad (31)$$

The evolving boundary layer on the two geometries already delivers a wide range of k_s^+ for a single test case. This can be easily predicted given the magnitude of the roughness height in the two cases, and the friction distribution along the plate, which ultimately plays a role in the scaling of k_s in wall units. By adopting different velocity values, minor changes are observed in corresponding k_s^+ values, slightly shifting data points and achieving a more robust and complete representation of the shifts. The cases naming and corresponding velocities that constitute the test matrix are presented in Table 2. A total of 6 simulation routines are required to gather the desired data points. The mesh characteristics presented in Sec. II.E are maintained constant for the same geometry at varying velocities, while verifying that the near-wall discretization was able to accommodate the estimated boundary layer thickening implied by a progressively reduced U_∞ .

Table 2 Simulation test cases. Labels **R**, **T**, **H** correspond to freestream velocities of U_∞ , $0.75 U_\infty$ and $0.5 U_\infty$.

Source Geometry [36]	Simulation Case	U_∞ [m/s]	$Re_L \cdot 10^{-5}$ [-]
113012.05	Case 1-R	6.67	3.85
113012.04	Case 2-R	6.67	3.85
113012.05	Case 1-T	5.00	2.89
113012.04	Case 2-T	5.00	2.89
113012.05	Case 1-H	3.33	1.93
113012.04	Case 2-H	3.33	1.93

III. Results

In the following sections, the main results of the present investigation are outlined. Firstly, the geometrical and statistical parameters of the rough surfaces under consideration are used to derive equivalent sand grain roughness distributions through the selected models. Then, turbulent mean profiles are analyzed, focusing on the log-layer development on top of the simulated ice geometries. From these profiles, roughness shifts are extracted and correlated to the considered k_s models, highlighting their dependence on specific roughness parameters. Finally, a brief assessment is made on $St - c_f$ analogies from literature based on the present results, and a multivariate statistical approach is employed to determine cross-dependencies of geometrical parameters with roughness shifts.

A. Ice roughness analysis

The method outlined in Sec. II.B is used to extract ice roughness properties. The resulting surface parameters distributions are presented in Fig. 4 for both geometries. Case 2 reflects the higher accretion time under which such iced

shape was obtained (see McCarrell et al. [36]). The skewness stays comparable in magnitude for both surfaces, showing an increasing trend along the plate. Indeed, even when considering roughness variation with respect to the mean height k_m , the nature of ice roughness is described by an inhomogeneous deposit of material onto the smooth substrate, leading to a mostly positive, increasing Sk . Physical reasoning already suggests that such value might introduce just a bias in k_s , since it does not show any evident variation when comparing two different accretion patterns. Among the parameters distributions, similar trends can be observed for the RMS roughness R_q and the slope quantifiers ES_x and α_{RMS} . This implies that such parameters are correlated on the same geometry, and might have a similar impact when used in a k_s model.

Fig. 4 Roughness parameters distribution for the two ice geometries under analysis. Dashed grey lines indicate locations for turbulent profiles evaluation (see Sec. III.B).

Figure 5 displays the k_s distributions in wall units derived from the models under investigation. The scaling is performed according to reference c_f distributions for the two geometries. A clear difference in magnitude can be spotted between the predictions among different models. In particular, the ones including the skewness as a parameter (i.e. Flack and Schultz [28] and Forooghi et al. [17]) tend to predict higher k_s values especially at locations further downstream along the plate with respect to slope- and shape-based models (such as Sigal and Danberg [26] and Bons [27]), confirming that the inclusion of such parameter may determine notable differences in k_s magnitude. Moreover, Flack and Schultz [28], Forooghi et al. [17], and Bons [27] predictions stay consistent between the two geometries, while for case 2 roughness Sigal and Danberg [26] evidently provides much higher k_s magnitudes, possibly due to substantially increased frontal area and solidity.

B. Mean turbulent profiles

The ELES results are post-processed to extract desired turbulent flow properties along the plate. In particular, mean velocity and thermal profiles are the focus of the analysis, as roughness shifts are directly computed from them as reported

Fig. 5 Equivalent sand grain roughness distributions in wall units derived from literature models for the present ice geometries. Left: Case 1; Right: Case 2.

in section II.F. The profiles are evaluated at the 10 progressive x/L locations reported in Table 3. These locations cover the rough zone, and feature a developing turbulent boundary layer. The evolution of the Reynolds number based on momentum thickness, Re_θ , is reported in Fig. 6. As can be seen from the graphs, transition happens around $x/L \sim 0.4$, point before which the Re_θ distribution agrees with the analytical smooth laminar trend $Re_{\theta, \text{lam}} = 0.664\sqrt{Re_x}$. In the turbulent region, the boundary layer thickness is increased on the rough surfaces with respect to the smooth turbulent reference $Re_{\theta, \text{turb}} = 0.016(Re_x)^{6/7}$.

The evaluation of the roughness shifts is physically relevant for those profiles presenting a detectable log-layer. The developing profiles in wall-units along the plate are partially shown (one each two stations, for clarity) in Figs. 7 and 8 for each velocity case. As expected, profiles evidence downward shifts with respect to the asymptotic smooth reference. The difference between the two tested geometries is highlighted in the graphs. Case 2 simulations show higher shifts, especially in terms of velocity, due to substantially higher roughness levels. In such case, the elements obstructing the boundary layer are evidently disrupting the log-layer up to further x/L locations with respect to case 1. Interestingly, the temperature profiles scaled in wall-units suggest minor dependence on local roughness, as the shifts are not varying drastically in magnitude. This aspect will be further cleared out in Sec. III.C. From the extracted mean turbulent

Table 3 Extraction points of boundary layer profiles along flat plate, with color legend for each velocity case.

Station ID	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
x/L [-]	0.57	0.60	0.63	0.65	0.68	0.71	0.73	0.76	0.79	0.81
Case *-R	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Case *-T	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Case *-H	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●

profiles, the log-layer detection is needed to finally extract the roughness shift values. According to the method outlined in Sec. II.F, the diagnostic functions K_u and K_θ are computed at the evaluation points x/L . To automatically detect the log-layer associated to the plateau of K_u and K_θ , the change in slope of these functions is considered, observing that a constant trend is always reached between changes in curvature of $\langle u \rangle^+$ and $\langle \theta \rangle^+$. By systematically applying this

Fig. 6 Re_θ distributions of cases 1-R and 2-R. Dashed lines mark locations for turbulent profiles extraction.

strategy, the roughness shifts evaluation point y_{rs}^+ can be taken as the mid-point between the log-layer bounds. The bounds resulting from this computation are also visually represented in Figs. 7 and 8. As can be observed, few velocity profiles for Case 2 geometries in the first evaluation points ($x/L = 0.57 - 0.65$) still present a transitional behavior, for which a clear log-layer identification becomes problematic. In addition to this, after transition takes place, the turbulent boundary layer presents itself with its smallest thickness, which is in the order of the roughness elements themselves. This implies that the roughness elements invade most of the boundary layer, questioning the existence of a log law. Therefore, roughness shifts associated to these points have to be carefully considered into the subsequent analysis, and eventually ruled out from the resulting conclusions.

Fig. 7 Mean turbulent profiles for Case 1 with detected log-layer bounds (squares), shifted vertically at progressive stations (--- Smooth log-layer, — 1-R, — 1-T, — 1-H).

C. Assessment of k_s correlations

The test cases count 3 velocities onto two different ice morphologies exhibiting disparate roughness heights, thus delivering a total of 60 evaluation points for any k_s^+ model evaluation. Each data set is plotted in wall units against the corresponding ΔU^+ and $\Delta \Theta^+$, according to the color legend found in Table 3. Moreover, each graph displays the

Fig. 8 Mean turbulent profiles for Case 2 with detected log-layer bounds (squares), shifted vertically at progressive stations (--- Smooth log-layer, — 2-R, — 2-T, — 2-H).

expected behavior for ΔU^+ and $\Delta \Theta^+$ with respect to k_s^+ according to literature. In the fully rough and transitional regime, ΔU^+ is modelled according to Eqs. (3) and (4), while the reference $\Delta \Theta^+$ follows the phenomenological model by Owen and Thomson [24] (Eq. 5) and the recent constant models of MacDonald et al. [18] and Rowin et al. [25].

Firstly, the Flack and Schultz [28] correlation (see Eq. 12) is employed to compute k_s^+ for each shift, and the resulting graphs are shown in Fig. 9. Such correlation was developed only to model skin friction effects, targeting the fully rough regime for a limited set of surfaces. Velocity shifts display a trend which approaches the fully rough asymptote for $k_s^+ > 400$, representing the highest ice roughness levels. Most of the points from case 2 cover this regime, as evidenced by the plot. Relatively to velocity shifts, the thermal shifts are misrepresented by the same model, as no clear trend could be identified. Indeed, the Flack and Schultz [28] correlation was not developed to account for heat transfer enhancement due to roughness. While a good portion of the points from case 1 falls around the expected constant values ($\Delta \Theta^+ \simeq 4$), no evident pattern is exhibited for the higher k_s^+ range.

The second correlation under analysis is the one proposed by Forooghi et al. [17], and the corresponding results are depicted in Fig. 10. k_s is computed according to Eq. (13), where effective slope effects are included together with surface skewness. The latter is almost always positive for rough surfaces generated by physical or engineering processes implying deposition, as in the case of ice accretion. While also Flack and Schultz [28] employed such parameter, it is reasonable to expect a negligible dependency of shifts on skewness for the specific case of ice roughness. Again, it must be observed that Forooghi et al. [17] built their correlation for modeling roughness effects on skin friction in the fully rough regime. These observations find feedback in the results. The plots of Fig. 10 showcase similar trends as the ones analyzed above. An improvement is registered moving towards the transitionally rough regime, with ΔU^+ approaching

Fig. 9 Flack and Schultz [28] correlation against computed velocity and thermal shifts.

Fig. 10 Forooghi et al. [17] correlation against computed velocity and thermal shifts.

slightly better the theoretical curve. This might suggest that slope effects are more important for the description of ice roughness friction enhancement, especially at lower k_s^+ . The thermal shifts still display ambiguous tendencies for both case 1 and 2, and the same observations made for Flack and Schultz [28] hold as well for the present model.

A different correlation was proposed by Sigal and Danberg [26], who introduced the solidity and shape parameter of Eq. (14), and k_s was then tuned as a function of such parameter in different ranges. Here, the correlation from Eq. (15) is used to link k_s^+ to the roughness shifts, reported in Fig. 11. With respect to the previous models, the range of k_s^+ values is considerably expanded, with points falling even below $k_s^+ = 5$. What can be observed for ΔU^+ is a relatively good collapse onto a curve that has a lower slope compared to the reference asymptotic behavior. This results in an over-predicted ΔU^+ at low k_s^+ , and the opposite effect at high k_s^+ . The wider k_s^+ seems to have an apparent beneficial effect on the thermal shifts collapse. $\Delta \Theta^+$ points are falling around the constant values predicted by literature studies [18, 25], with a slight increase for the higher roughness levels ($k_s^+ > 100$). For k_s^+ approaching 1000, a reduction is observed which aligns better with the phenomenological model of Owen and Thomson [24], and may be physically associated by localized recirculation zones that shield the region from convective effects.

Lastly, the model by Bons [27] is used to evaluate k_s , and the resulting correlation with the shifts is visualized in Fig. 12. Bons [27] introduced a k_s fully dependent on surface slope effects, by considering only roughness elements exposed

Fig. 11 Sigal and Danberg [26] correlation against computed velocity and thermal shifts.

Fig. 12 Bons [27] correlation against computed velocity and thermal shifts.

significantly to the flow. An important aspect of such correlation is that was derived on realistic wind turbine rough samples in a ZPG wind tunnel setup, taking into account also heat transfer effects. Moreover, Bons [27] introduced corrections for the transitionally rough regime, delivering a model which is expected to perform better in this range of k_s^+ . Indeed, looking at the graphs of Fig. 12, the ΔU^+ exhibits a collapse that correctly capture the expected slope of the Grigson' [21] prediction, with a substantial improvement in the transitionally rough regime with respect to the previous models. A slightly better distribution is also shown by $\Delta \Theta^+$ for mid to low k_s^+ , again followed by the same reduction registered for the previous model around very high k_s^+ . As previously observed, it appears that the characterization of thermal shifts is hindered by a limited comprehension of how roughness affects heat transfer enhancement. In general, the analyzed data points do not display a consistent pattern and do not align well with findings from the literature.

D. Assessment of $St - c_f$ analogies

The trends of c_f and St along the plate can be extracted according to Eqs. 24 and 25. These were used as validation parameters in Sotomayor-Zakharov et al. [48]. In this section, a brief assessment of existing $St - c_f$ analogies is proposed, according to the models described in Sec. II.D, having as a reference the c_f and St distribution delivered by simulations. While the Martinelli [29] analogy can be readily computed from c_f and dimensionless flow parameters,

the formulas by Owen and Thomson [24] and Forooghi et al. [32] (Eqs. (18) and (19)) require k_s^+ . To unambiguously determine k_s^+ based on friction, the Grigson's correlation [21] introduced in Eq. (4) is used in combination with ΔU^+ values from ELES profiles.

Skin friction results from ELES are presented in Fig. 13. From the plots, the increase in global friction is evident between case 1-R and case 2-R, testifying the enhanced pressure drag induced by higher roughness. Indeed, by deriving St from a classical Reynolds analogy, i.e. $St \sim 0.5 c_f Pr_t^{-1}$, the estimate is leading to an overestimation of the convective heat transfer which grows significantly when the pressure contribution to c_f is predominant over the viscous one. $St - c_f$ analogies in literature have tried to correct for this unbalance.

The estimates resulting from the $St - c_f$ analogies applied in the present analysis are presented in Fig. 14, alongside the corresponding relative error with respect to the simulation results. The latter is computed as $e_{r\%} = 100 \cdot (|St_a - St_{ELES}| / St_{ELES})$, being St_a obtained from the analogies. Only reference cases 1-R and 2-R are considered for this purpose.

Fig. 13 c_f trends from ELES. Left: Case 1-R; Right: Case 2-R.

Fig. 14 $St - c_f$ analogies and relative errors with respect to ELES trends. Left: Case 1-R; Right: Case 2-R.

Firstly, it can be noted how the best performance is achieved on irregular roughness by the Owen and Thomson [24] analogy, which delivers the lowest error across the two cases. This is expected, as the relation was acknowledged by

previous icing applications for providing acceptable approximations on irregular roughness [3, 10, 13, 16]. For case 1-R, in presence of lower roughness, the analogy by Forooghi et al. [32] is able to capture St in the turbulent region with acceptable accuracy, delivering errors within 20 %. This is a symptom of general applicability of such correlation, that as anticipated has been obtained from a different numerical dataset on artificial and realistic roughness. The Martinelli [29] analogy underestimates the local St with higher mismatch. However, the same analogy has comparable performance for case 2-R, showing low sensitivity to the geometry. On the other hand, the Forooghi et al. [32] estimate depending on k_s^+ highlights a poorer performance with respect to case 1, while still delivering lower errors with respect to Martinelli - except for points with local friction peaks. The overall results indicate an acceptable performance from the Owen and Thomson [24] analogy, which however still suffers from significant errors on higher roughness (case 2). The other models highlighted limited accuracy in the application to the analyzed realistic ice morphologies, as St_a is not able to reproduce closely trends directly computed and validated through ELES. Nevertheless, the simple model by Forooghi et al. [32] delivers lower errors which testify its applicability in disparate studies, as already noted by Peeters and Sandham [33]. Additionally, the outcomes indicate the need for a more thorough physics-based study on disparate ice roughness topology, where Reynolds-like analogies fail to capture the mechanism ruling the interplay between momentum and scalar transport.

E. Multivariate analysis of rough surfaces

In this section, the outcomes of a multivariate analysis are reported to highlight possible cross-dependencies in roughness geometrical parameters, including their relation to shifts. To this aim, cases 1-R and 2-R are selected, representing the baseline for each rough geometry at hand. The aim is to analyze cross-correlation among different parameters reported within the same matrix plot, shown in Figs. 15 and 16. On the diagonal, histograms representing the discrete probability distribution of each parameter are depicted for each case. For clarity, a limited number of parameters is considered for each evaluation. In particular, two evaluations are presented with a different set of parameters. The first evaluation is reported in Fig. 15, for which main geometrical roughness indicators are taken into account. These indicators are the ones mainly used by equivalent sand grain roughness models, i.e. R_q , Sk , ES_x and α_{RMS} , and that characterize the correlations proposed by Flack and Schultz [28], Forooghi et al. [17] and Bons [27]. The same plot include two additional entries for ΔU^+ and $\Delta \Theta^+$. When applied to the simulated ice geometries, the analysis reveals an expected cross-dependence between slope indicators such as ES_x and α_{RMS} . These two parameters show a clear quasi-linear relation with the RMS roughness height R_q , suggesting a possible similar influence on the flow. Indeed, ΔU^+ exhibits a power-law interaction with all these three quantities, revealing their potential in describing the behavior of velocity shifts, and justifying their employment for ice roughness correlations as well. Similar trends of ΔU^+ with respect to ES_x can be found for example in the study of Yuan and Piomelli [39] on realistic ice morphologies. Contrarily, none of these cross-dependent parameters show a relation with $\Delta \Theta^+$, confirming the criticality in the description of

thermal effects through the same correlations found for the velocity shifts. The last parameter left is the skewness, which presents a random scatter with respect to any other matrix plot input. In the present case, skewness is influenced by the physical phenomenon that leads to ice roughness generation, which is driven by a deposit of material onto a previously smooth surface. The resulting rough pattern is inhomogeneous with varying thickness, i.e. varying mean. This results in mostly positive, increasing Sk levels, as shown in 4 and reported among others by McClain et al. [57]. Such physical aspect represents an important difference with respect to regular, sand grain, and random homogeneous roughness employed for the development of k_s models by Flack and Schultz [28] and Forooghi et al. [17]. Indeed, such models revealed a relation between Sk and other statistical parameters, as shown in a similar multivariate analysis performed on rough surface by Jouybari et al. [58]. This possibly highlights the necessity of using a set of different parameters for ice roughness k_s treatment. That is why a second evaluation is performed considering different roughness geometrical parameters, briefly described in what follows. The kurtosis Ku (see (7e)) is introduced as an additional statistical moment, representing the nature of the surface texture in terms of pronounced peaks or valleys. Additionally, the local roughness wavelength λ_x , defined as the mean peak-to-peak streamwise distance for a given region, is computed. S_{corr} represents the corrected wetted area ratio, defined by Aupoix [22] as the ratio $S_{w,corr}/S$, being $S_{w,corr}$ the wetted area

Fig. 15 Cross-dependence of main roughness parameters and computed roughness shifts. Cases at reference velocity (\bullet 1-R, \bullet 2-R) are reported.

Fig. 16 Cross-dependence of additional roughness parameters and computed roughness shifts. Cases at reference velocity (• 1-R, • 2-R) are reported.

corrected by considering only the exposed surface elements above k_m . Lastly, the shape parameter Λ_s by Sigal and Danberg [26] is taken into account. Cross-dependences are found between S_{corr} and Λ_s , both related to area ratios. An inverse relation $S_{\text{corr}} \sim 1/\Lambda_s$ can also be detected, and once again a power-law dependence of ΔU^+ on such parameters is individuated. The other matrix plot entries are apparently unrelated, with $\Delta\Theta^+$ once again uncorrelated to all parameters. In Aupoix [9], the maximum thermal shift $\Delta\Theta_{\text{max}}^+$ was linked to S_{corr} by observing a possible trend from data on various regular roughness shapes. However, the same relation is not registered for the present irregular surfaces between the computed $\Delta\Theta^+$ and S_{corr} , and this can be ascribed to the type of roughness considered. While the simplified multivariate approach used in this study does not allow a thorough testing of parameters combinations and their possible relation to shifts, it is still meaningful to check which standalone indicator can describe better roughness effects on the mean flow. It is then clear that, while the analysis confirms the potential usefulness of R_q , ES_x , α_{RMS} , or Λ_s and S_{corr} in building k_s correlations with respect to velocity shifts, other commonly adopted indicators such as Sk could be ruled out for ice geometries generated by deposition. At the same time, the limitation of existing correlations that combine those parameters in describing thermal effects is confirmed, as none of such quantities is showing a cross-dependence with $\Delta\Theta^+$. Further analysis of other parameters or their cross-combination would be required to devise new k_s correlations usable to account jointly for momentum and thermal effects. Nevertheless, this is currently out of scope of the present

work.

IV. Conclusion

The proposed analysis employed ELES to address the investigation of skin friction and convective heat transfer enhancement on realistic ice roughness, with a focus on currently available equivalent sand grain roughness models and $St - c_f$ analogies from literature. A ZPG heated flat plate setup is reproduced from the experiments of McCarrell et al. [36], following the validated setup studied by Sotomayor-Zakharov et al. [48].

The velocity shifts, in general, have an acceptable collapse onto the expected fully rough asymptote at high roughness levels for most of the models, with the only exception of Sigal and Danberg [26]. For the latter, ΔU^+ collapses onto a curve characterized by a lower slope with respect to the reference. Towards lower k_s^+ , the transitionally rough regime is well represented only by the correlation of Bons [27], while skewness-based models seem to be affected by an underprediction of ΔU^+ for $k_s^+ < 400$. The reason may also be found in the nature of such correlations. Indeed, Flack and Schultz [28] and Forooghi et al. [17] derived them specifically for the fully rough regime on artificially generated roughness. Still, the outcome suggests a potential use of slope-related parameter for development of icing specific k_s^+ correlations for skin friction.

On the other hand, thermal shifts are misrepresented by all the considered models. $\Delta\Theta^+$ values do not exhibit any clear patterns when using the correlations of Flack and Schultz [28] and Forooghi et al. [17], with slight improvements offered by the other correlations. In particular, both Sigal and Danberg [26] and Bons [27] seem to predict a collapse of $\Delta\Theta^+$ around a constant value $\simeq 4$, aligned with previous literature observations [18, 25], only for $k_s^+ < 100$. On the other hand, for higher values of k_s^+ , the tendency shows an initial growth and successive decrease of $\Delta\Theta^+$, more in accordance with older phenomenological models [24]. This is especially observed for case 2 geometries, which strongly obstruct the boundary layer flow. The brief analysis of $St - c_f$ analogies resulting from simulation results showed, for the reference cases, a discrete performance of the more recent model from Forooghi et al. [32], which demonstrated its applicability in a TBL context on inhomogeneous roughness, and confirmed the validity of the analogy from Owen and Thomson [24] on irregular roughness.

The multivariate analysis performed on the available rough surfaces aimed at isolating possible cross-correlation between roughness parameters and shifts. Several parameters showed a clear interaction, such as R_q with the slope indicators ES_x , α_{RMS} , and Λ_s with S_{corr} , both related to the exposed rough surface. ΔU^+ confirmed dependence on these set of variables, which enter the tested k_s models. Once more, no evident pattern was observed between $\Delta\Theta^+$ and the computed surface indicators.

To conclude, this study highlights the peculiar nature of ice-induced roughness and its impact on turbulent boundary layers, showing that commonly used equivalent sand grain roughness models may not fully capture the resulting flow modifications. By systematically testing k_s correlations against realistic ice geometries, the analysis provides new

insights into their ability to reproduce flow shifts and limitations in accounting for thermal effects. Moreover, an overview of the influence of diverse geometrical parameters on computed shifts is delivered. The analysis demonstrates that, while geometry-based k_s models remain a practical tool, their predictive capability is challenged by the complexity of ice morphologies. This aspect also emerges in the behavior of $St - c_f$ analogies, where ice roughness impacts the conventional assumptions underlying heat–momentum transfer relations. Importantly, this work establishes a comprehensive overview of how roughness–flow interactions manifest on icing surfaces, laying the groundwork for more reliable predictive strategies in aero-icing contexts.

Acknowledgments

R.G. has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101072551 (TRACES). M.G. has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101206621 (RESET).

We gratefully acknowledge Dr. Stephen McClain for providing us the experimental database and for the fruitful discussions regarding the physical aspects of the research.

The authors gratefully acknowledge the computing time made available to them on the high-performance computer "Lise" at the NHR Center NHR@ZIB. This center is jointly supported by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research and the state governments participating in the NHR (www.nhr-verein.de/unsere-partner).

References

- [1] Wright, W. B., Porter, C. E., Galloway, E. T., and Rigby, D. L., “GlennICE 2.1 Capabilities and Results,” *AIAA Aviation 2022 Forum*, 2022, p. 3309. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2022-3309>.
- [2] Beaugendre, H., Morency, F., and Habashi, W. G., “FENSAP-ICE’s Three-Dimensional In-Flight Ice Accretion Module: ICE3D,” *Journal of Aircraft*, Vol. 40, No. 2, 2003, pp. 239–247. <https://doi.org/10.2514/2.3113>.
- [3] Trontin, P., Blanchard, G., Kontogiannis, A., and Villedieu, P., “Description and assessment of the new ONERA 2D icing suite IGLOO2D,” *9th AIAA atmospheric and space environments conference*, 2017, p. 3417. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2017-3417>.
- [4] Gallia, M., Rausa, A., Martuffo, A., and Guardone, A., “A Comprehensive Numerical Model for Numerical Simulation of Ice Accretion and Electro-Thermal Ice Protection System in Anti-icing and De-icing Mode, with an Ice Shedding Analysis,” Tech. Rep. 2023-01-1463, SAE International, Jun. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.4271/2023-01-1463>.
- [5] Sotomayor-Zakharov, D., Sobotta, B., and Knop, I., “A dynamic collection efficiency formulation implemented in the icing code DICEPS,” *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, Vol. 217, 2023, p. 124590. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2023.124590>.

- [6] Laurendeau, E., Bourgault-Cote, S., Ozcer, I. A., Hann, R., Radenac, E., and Pueyo, A., “Summary from the 1st AIAA ice prediction workshop,” *AIAA Aviation 2022 Forum*, 2022, p. 3398. <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.2514/6.2022-3398>.
- [7] Laurendeau, E., Blanchet, M., Zayni, M. K., Hann, R., Radenac, E., Mussa, I., and Pueyo, A., “Summary from the 2nd AIAA Ice Prediction Workshop,” *AIAA Aviation 2024 Forum and Ascend*, 2024, p. 3604. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2024-3604>.
- [8] Han, Y., and Palacios, J., “Surface roughness and heat transfer improved predictions for aircraft ice-accretion modeling,” *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 55, No. 4, 2017, pp. 1318–1331. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.J055217>.
- [9] Aupoix, B., “Improved heat transfer predictions on rough surfaces,” *International Journal of Heat and Fluid Flow*, Vol. 56, 2015, pp. 160–171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatfluidflow.2015.07.007>.
- [10] Radenac, E., Kontogiannis, A., Bayeux, C., and Villedieu, P., “An extended rough-wall model for an integral boundary layer model intended for ice accretion calculations,” *2018 Atmospheric and Space Environments Conference*, 2018, p. 2858. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2018-2858>.
- [11] Colebrook, C. F., and White, C. M., “Experiments with fluid friction in roughened pipes,” *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A-Mathematical and Physical Sciences*, Vol. 161, No. 906, 1937, pp. 367–381. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspa.1937.0150>.
- [12] Nikuradse, J., “Laws of flow in rough pipes,” *NACA Technical Memorandum*, , No. 1292, 1950.
- [13] Wright, W. B., “A summary of validation results for LEWICE 2.0,” *37th Aerospace Sciences Meeting and Exhibit*, 1999, p. 249. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.1999-249>.
- [14] McClain, S. T., Vargas, M., Tsao, J.-C., Broeren, A. P., and Lee, S., “Ice accretion roughness measurements and modeling,” *European Conference for Aeronautics and Space Sciences (EUCASS) 2017*, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.13009/EUCASS2017-555>.
- [15] Sotomayor-Zakharov, D., Radenac, E., Gallia, M., Guardone, A., and Knop, I., “Statistical analysis of the surface roughness on aircraft icing,” *Journal of Aircraft*, Vol. 61, No. 1, 2024, pp. 245–256. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.C037403>.
- [16] Ignatowicz, K., Morency, F., and Beaugendre, H., “Data-driven roughness estimation for glaze ice accretion simulation,” Tech. Rep. 2023-01-1449, SAE International, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.4271/2023-01-1449>.
- [17] Forooghi, P., Stroh, A., Magagnato, F., Jakirlić, S., and Frohnäpfel, B., “Toward a universal roughness correlation,” *Journal of Fluids Engineering*, Vol. 139, No. 12, 2017, p. 121201. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4037280>.
- [18] MacDonald, M., Hutchins, N., and Chung, D., “Roughness effects in turbulent forced convection,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 861, 2019, pp. 138–162. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2018.900>.
- [19] Jiménez, J., “Turbulent flows over rough walls,” *Annu. Rev. Fluid Mech.*, Vol. 36, No. 1, 2004, pp. 173–196. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.fluid.36.050802.122103>.

- [20] Kadivar, M., Tormey, D., and McGranaghan, G., “A review on turbulent flow over rough surfaces: fundamentals and theories,” *International Journal of Thermofluids*, Vol. 10, 2021, p. 100077. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijft.2021.100077>.
- [21] Grigson, C., “Drag losses of new ships caused by hull finish,” *Journal of Ship Research*, Vol. 36, No. 02, 1992, pp. 182–196. <https://doi.org/10.5957/jsr.1992.36.2.182>.
- [22] Aupoix, B., “Roughness corrections for the $k-\omega$ shear stress transport model: status and proposals,” *Journal of Fluids Engineering*, Vol. 137, No. 2, 2015, p. 021202. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4028122>.
- [23] Zhong, K., Hutchins, N., and Chung, D., “Heat-transfer scaling at moderate Prandtl numbers in the fully rough regime,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 959, 2023, p. A8. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2023.125>.
- [24] Owen, P., and Thomson, W., “Heat transfer across rough surfaces,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 15, No. 3, 1963, pp. 321–334. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112063000288>.
- [25] Rowin, W. A., Zhong, K., Saurav, T., Jelly, T., Hutchins, N., and Chung, D., “Modelling the effect of roughness density on turbulent forced convection,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 979, 2024, p. A22. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2023.1063>.
- [26] Sigal, A., and Danberg, J. E., “New correlation of roughness density effect on the turbulent boundary layer,” *AIAA journal*, Vol. 28, No. 3, 1990, pp. 554–556. <https://doi.org/10.2514/3.10427>.
- [27] Bons, J. P., “St and cf Augmentation for Real Turbine Roughness With Elevated Freestream Turbulence,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 124, No. 4, 2002, pp. 632–644. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.1505851>.
- [28] Flack, K. A., and Schultz, M. P., “Review of Hydraulic Roughness Scales in the Fully Rough Regime,” *Journal of Fluids Engineering*, Vol. 132, No. 4, 2010, p. 041203. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4001492>.
- [29] Martinelli, R. C., “Heat transfer to molten metals,” *Transactions of the American Society of Mechanical Engineers*, Vol. 69, No. 8, 1947, pp. 947–956. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4017600>.
- [30] Yaglom, A., and Kader, B., “Heat and mass transfer between a rough wall and turbulent fluid flow at high Reynolds and Peclet numbers,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 62, No. 3, 1974, pp. 601–623. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112074000838>.
- [31] Bons, J., “A critical assessment of Reynolds analogy for turbine flows,” *J. Heat Transfer*, Vol. 127, No. 5, 2005, pp. 472–485. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.1861919>.
- [32] Forooghi, P., Stripf, M., and Frohnafel, B., “A systematic study of turbulent heat transfer over rough walls,” *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, Vol. 127, 2018, pp. 1157–1168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2018.08.013>.
- [33] Peeters, J., and Sandham, N., “Turbulent heat transfer in channels with irregular roughness,” *International journal of heat and mass transfer*, Vol. 138, 2019, pp. 454–467. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2019.04.013>.
- [34] Shannon, T. A., and McClain, S. T., “Convection from a Simulated NACA 0012 with Icing Roughness of Different Shape and Thermal Conductivity,” *8th AIAA Atmospheric and Space Environments Conference*, American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, 2016, p. 3588. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2016-3588>.

- [35] Hawkins, D. M., Shannon, T. A., and McClain, S. T., “Convection from Surfaces with Real Laser-Scanned Ice Accretion Roughness and Different Thermal Conductivities,” *9th AIAA Atmospheric and Space Environments Conference*, American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2017-3579>.
- [36] McCarrell, J. L., Shannon, T. A., and McClain, S. T., “Convection from Surfaces with Ice Roughness Characterized at Increasing Accumulation Times,” *2018 Atmospheric and Space Environments Conference*, 2018, p. 3016. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2018-3016>.
- [37] Stebbins, S. J., Loth, E., Broeren, A. P., and Potapczuk, M., “Review of computational methods for aerodynamic analysis of iced lifting surfaces,” *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, Vol. 111, 2019, p. 100583. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paerosci.2019.100583>.
- [38] Bornhoft, B., Jain, S. S., Goc, K., Bose, S. T., and Moin, P., “Large-eddy simulations of the NACA23012 airfoil with laser-scanned ice shapes,” *Aerospace Science and Technology*, Vol. 146, 2024, p. 108957. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2024.108957>.
- [39] Yuan, J., and Piomelli, U., “Estimation and prediction of the roughness function on realistic surfaces,” *Journal of Turbulence*, Vol. 15, No. 6, 2014, pp. 350–365. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14685248.2014.907904>.
- [40] Yang, J., Stroh, A., Chung, D., and Forooghi, P., “Direct numerical simulation-based characterization of pseudo-random roughness in minimal channels,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 941, 2022, p. A47. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2022.331>.
- [41] Yang, J., Velandia, J., Bansmer, S., Stroh, A., and Forooghi, P., “A comparison of hydrodynamic and thermal properties of artificially generated against realistic rough surfaces,” *International Journal of Heat and Fluid Flow*, Vol. 99, 2023, p. 109093. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatfluidflow.2022.109093>.
- [42] Piomelli, U., “Recent advances in the numerical simulation of rough-wall boundary layers,” *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth, Parts A/B/C*, Vol. 113, 2019, pp. 63–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pce.2018.10.005>.
- [43] Yuan, J., and Piomelli, U., “Numerical simulations of sink-flow boundary layers over rough surfaces,” *Physics of Fluids*, Vol. 26, No. 1, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4862672>.
- [44] Yuan, J., and Piomelli, U., “Numerical simulation of a spatially developing accelerating boundary layer over roughness,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 780, 2015, pp. 192–214. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2015.437>.
- [45] Ananth, S. M., Sabapathy, S., Vadlamani, N. R., and Coull, J., “The Impact of Real Roughness Features on Boundary Layer Transition,” *Flow, Turbulence and Combustion*, Vol. 114, No. 3, 2025, pp. 737–763. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10494-024-00605-8>.
- [46] Cardillo, J., Chen, Y., Araya, G., Newman, J., Jansen, K., and Castillo, L., “DNS of a turbulent boundary layer with surface roughness,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 729, 2013, pp. 603–637. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2013.326>.
- [47] Zabaleta, F., Bornhoft, B., Jain, S. S., Bose, S. T., and Moin, P., “Large-eddy simulations of heat transfer from iced surfaces,” *Center for Turbulence Research Annual Research Briefs 2024*, 2024, pp. 29–40. URL <https://ctr.stanford.edu/publications/annual-research-briefs/annual-research-briefs-2024>.

- [48] Sotomayor-Zakharov, D., Gaudioso, R., and Gallia, M., “Embedded LES of a turbulent thermal boundary layer over ice roughness,” *Computers Fluids*, 2025, p. 106652. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compfluid.2025.106652>.
- [49] McClain, S. T., and Boldt, R., “Equivalent Sand-Grain Roughness Parameter Evaluation of Scanned Ice Accretion Geometries,” *AIAA AVIATION FORUM AND ASCEND 2024*, 2024, p. 4002. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2024-4002>.
- [50] McClain, S. T., Reed, D., Vargas, M. M., Kreeger, R. E., and Tsao, J.-C., “Ice Roughness in Short Duration SLD Icing Events,” *6th AIAA Atmospheric and Space Environments Conference*, 2014, p. 2330. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2014-2330>.
- [51] McClain, S. T., and Kreeger, R. E., “Assessment of Ice Shape Roughness Using a Self-Organizing Map Approach,” *5th AIAA Atmospheric and Space Environments Conference*, 2013, p. 2546. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2013-2546>.
- [52] Busse, A., Lützner, M., and Sandham, N. D., “Direct numerical simulation of turbulent flow over a rough surface based on a surface scan,” *Computers & Fluids*, Vol. 116, 2015, pp. 129–147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compfluid.2015.04.008>.
- [53] Nicoud, F., and Ducros, F., “Subgrid-scale stress modelling based on the square of the velocity gradient tensor,” *Flow, turbulence and Combustion*, Vol. 62, No. 3, 1999, pp. 183–200. <https://doi.org/10.1023/a:1009995426001>.
- [54] Menter, F. R., “Two-equation eddy-viscosity turbulence models for engineering applications,” *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 32, No. 8, 1994, pp. 1598–1605. <https://doi.org/10.2514/3.12149>.
- [55] Menter, F. R., Langtry, R. B., Likki, S., Suzen, Y. B., Huang, P., and Völker, S., “A correlation-based transition model using local variables - Part I: model formulation,” *Journal of turbomachinery*, Vol. 128, No. 3, 2006, pp. 413–422. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.2184352>.
- [56] Piomelli, U., and Yuan, J., “Numerical simulations of spatially developing, accelerating boundary layers,” *Physics of Fluids*, Vol. 25, No. 10, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4825033>.
- [57] McClain, S. T., Vargas, M. M., Tsao, J.-C., and Broeren, A. P., “A model for ice accretion roughness evolution and spatial variations,” *AIAA Aviation 2021 Forum*, 2021, p. 2641. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2021-2641>.
- [58] Jouybari, M. A., Yuan, J., Brereton, G. J., and Murillo, M. S., “Data-driven prediction of the equivalent sand-grain height in rough-wall turbulent flows,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 912, 2021, p. A8. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2020.1085>.